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Contents

Introduction	5
A Comprehensive Social Policy for Inter-State Migrant Workers in Kerala, India: Identifying the Gaps, Challenges and Way Forward <i>Anjali J. & Navas M. Khadar</i>	11
Interstate Guest Workers in Kerala: Intersectional Perspectives and State's Response <i>Anjali Borhade, Isha Jain, & Subhojit Dey</i>	26
A Critical Analysis of Interstate Migrant Legislation in India <i>Basavaraj M. Kubakaddi & Ragini Rajbhor</i>	43
Labour and Workplace Security of Tamil Female Unorganized Workers of Cardamom Plantations in Munnar <i>Renjith K.R. & Bijulal M.V.</i>	62
Space, Migration, Identity and Mobility – Life Stories of Migrant Tea Workers in Kerala <i>Athulya S. & Rekha Raj</i>	74
Economic Development and Challenges of Inter-state migrants working in Kerala <i>Jenikrishna M.U. & P. P. Naushad</i>	84
Financial Well-being of Interstate Migrant Labourers- the Role of Financial Behaviour <i>Abdul Gafoor K. P. & Amilan S.</i>	95
Effect of Exclusionary Politics on Immigrant Labour Force in India: An Analytical Study <i>Subham Kumar Kanu</i>	108
Difficulties with Social Stigma and Ethnocentrism Among Migrant Labourers in Kerala <i>Devi Chandana M. & Shibu M.P.</i>	119
Health-Related Challenges among Interstate Migrants in Kerala, India: A Study of Ernakulum District <i>Megha Madhavan E.V. & Uma Purushothaman</i>	135

In-Migrant Labourers' Lived Experiences in Kerala Amidst the Covid-19 Pandemic <i>Athitha Sunil & Lirar Pulikkalakath</i>	145
Refugees: The Classless, Stateless Society? <i>Jose Deepak T.T., Jerry Mathew Abraham & Mathew A. Varghese</i>	160
Racial Profiling of Immigrants: Do Some Bodies Matter More? <i>Manjima Anjana & Tanay Thakur</i>	175
The Burden of an Immigrant: Methods of Exclusion in Assam <i>Samik Roy Chowdhury</i>	191
Beyond Binaries; Queer Migration Reasons and Question of Inclusion in Data Collection <i>Teena Mariya Saju and Dinoop K</i>	200
Climate-Induced Migration to India's Megacities: Exploring Questions of Migrant Inclusivity in Mitigation Strategies <i>Divya Balan & Tanvi Saxena</i>	215
Contributors	230

A Comprehensive Social Policy for Inter-State Migrant Workers in Kerala, India: Identifying the Gaps, Challenges and Way Forward

Anjali J.* & Navas M. Khadar**

Abstract

Going by the 2011 Census figures, approximately 456 million people in India are on the move, accounting for about 37 per cent of the country's population. A decade down the line, surpassing China to become the world's most populous country (with the count hovering around 1.42 billion in 2022), coupled with the paradox of demographic dividend, whereby two out of every three Indians are under 35 years of age, the migration wave is undoubtedly set to intensify in the coming years. According to UNESCO (2013) and ILO (2020) estimates, these internal migrants contribute 10 per cent to India's GDP, by serving as the backbone of several major sectors such as construction and transportation, across its emerging economy. On the flip side, the imminent surge in migration threatens to exacerbate the challenges of efficient resource distribution, infrastructure development and creation of adequate employment opportunities. Further, the migrant crisis that unfolded during the Covid-19 pandemic-induced lockdown, has exposed the lack of a sound internal migration policy in the country, directed at the protection and welfare of its 'invisible workforce'. As such, it becomes imperative to undertake meaningful deliberations to formulate effective national, state and local policies to ensure the occupational health, safety and social security of inter-state migrant workers in India. In the light of the above discussion, the present paper focuses on analysing the challenges that persist in integrating the migrant community into the socio-economic and political fabric of Kerala, against the backdrop of the overall migration scenario in the state. Further, the paper also critically examines the gaps and challenges in the existing migration policies and migrant welfare initiatives as envisaged by the state, besides suggesting policy recommendations based on best practices worth emulating.

Key Words: Kerala, Labour Migration, Social Integration, Policy Intervention, Welfare Schemes.

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Tracing a Hundred Years: The Kerala Migration Story

Scholars like K.V. Joseph noted that Kerala saw significant cross-border migration in the early 20th century. K.V. Joseph meticulously documented Keralites' migration to other Indian states between 1900 and 1930. There are significant mentions in the Malayalam literature on this migration. Vailoppilli Sreedhara Menon's 1947 poem *Assam Panikkar* from *Kannikoythu* poignantly depicts Kerala's working class's World War II migration to Assam. Because of poverty, hunger, and feudal oppression, these migrants left their homeland. The poem powerfully captures their sorrow, compulsion, and resilience. Their emotional turmoil and desperation are shown by "cursing their homeland". Set in a wartime military camp, the poem emphasises global conflict's impact on labour migration.

At the turn of the century, Kerala began attracting Tamil Nadu and Karnataka migrant workers for agriculture, construction, and trade. According to K.C.Zachariah, these workers transformed Kerala's agrarian economy by making non-Malayalee labourers common in the fields. From 1930 to 1960, interstate migration, especially in agriculture, increased, creating a symbiotic relationship between migrants and locals. Before Kerala became a state in 1957, migrant workers from other states were called "other state workers," despite their vital socio-economic contributions. When the Indian Parliament passed the Interstate Migrant Workmen Act in 1979, interstate migration became a major socio-economic issue. In 1980, Kerala's migrant workers gained legal recognition and protection.

Oil-boom driven mass migration of Keralites to GCC countries in the 1960s marked a turning point. The 1960s and 1970s saw this wave of migration transform Kerala's economy. According to Rejimon Kuttapan (2021), over 3 million Keralites migrated to the Gulf during this time, helping the state develop and modernise. People from various socio-economic backgrounds, skilled and unskilled, migrated to the Gulf for better opportunities. This mass exodus left agriculture, construction, and plantations short-staffed. From the 1960s to the 1990s, Kerala relied on Tamil Nadu and Karnataka migrant workers to fill the gap, sustaining its economy. The 1990s saw Kerala's youth leave traditional jobs abroad for better-paying blue- and white-collar jobs. This increased the local labour shortage, attracting interstate migrants to agriculture, brickmaking, plantations, and construction (Peter & Narendran, 2017). Palakkad, Wayanad, and Idukki field studies found multi-generational migrant communities, highlighting Kerala's long-term demographic and economic effects from interstate migration.

Kerala's migration patterns have changed since the 1990s, with the opening

of a new corridor from Eastern and Northeastern India. Kerala's socio-economic and cultural landscape changes as Assam, West Bengal, Bihar, Jharkhand, and Odisha migrants flow in (Peter & Gupta, 2012). Census 2011 data confirm this shift, showing these states' growing migration share in Kerala. The Anusandhan National Research Foundation (ANRF) study 2022-2025 shows that people from West Bengal, Assam, Jharkhand and Odisha migrated \square more to Kerala. These migrant communities have integrated into different sectors based on their skills and experience. West Bengal migrants dominate Kerala's construction industry, boosting infrastructure while Assam workers help grow the wood and plywood industry in Kallayi and Kozhikode. Due to their adaptability, Jharkhand and Bihar migrants have filled manual labour shortages. In contrast, Odisha migrants have contributed to improve the gold and textile industries with their artisanal skills (Kerala Institute of Labour and Employment, 2020).

This new migration stream has reduced Kerala's labour shortages and increased cultural diversity. Migration has enriched Kerala's language, cuisines, and traditions, boosting economic productivity and social cohesion. Kerala receives 30.6% of its workforce from interstate migrants, ranking fifth nationally (NSSO (MSPI, 2020–21). According to the Census 2011, West Bengal is the top source state, followed by Assam, Bihar, Jharkhand, Chhattisgarh, and Manipur. The Kerala State Planning Board (2021) estimates 3.4 million migrant workers, rising to 5 million by 2050. Over 14,000 migrant families live in Kerala. The 2023 ANRF-funded study, *Effect of Social, Institutional, and Technological Interventions on Access to Healthcare Among Interstate Migrant Labourers in Kerala*, found that migrant workers in Kerala work in over 80 job categories, earning daily wages between \square 500 and \square 1,400. These figures highlight the need to examine two key dimensions: the push factors driving migration from across India and the pull factors that make Kerala a top destination for interstate migrant workers.

In Search of Greener Pastures

Studies point towards the declining agricultural productivity as well as the existing disguised unemployment in the primary sector coupled with the increasing frequency of natural calamities such as massive floods and severe droughts owing to climate change, to be the most compelling reasons behind migration. Besides, the rapidly rising population, especially in states such as Uttar Pradesh and Bihar, prevalence of caste-based violence as well as the lack of adequate and stable employment opportunities have also been identified as significant factors propelling the outflux of population.

Having said that, extensive field surveys undertaken across 40 villages

spanning 5 districts of West Bengal by the ANRF (Mahatma Gandhi University, 2022-2025a) project have revealed that the relatively favourable socio-cultural milieu that differ markedly from other states, availability of regular employment and adequate educational opportunities, as well as higher minimum wages to be the prominent factors that draw migrants to Kerala. According to estimates of the Reserve Bank of India, as of 2022, Kerala offered the highest daily wage rates in India, even double the national average, across both agricultural as well as non-agricultural sectors. Also, when compared to other cities of the country, where the cost of living (including food and rent) is exorbitantly high, Kerala offers better living standards at reasonable costs.

Moreover, often perceived as a relatively peaceful state with a cosmopolitan environment, Kerala provides the much-needed political stability and escape from the clutches of caste-based discriminations. This proposition is substantiated by the fact that districts having the highest proportion of scheduled castes, scheduled tribes and religious minorities as a percentage of their respective populations in India are at the forefront of contributing migrants to Kerala. Also, four of the five districts with the highest proportion of Dalit population in India have been found to actively contribute migrants to Kerala (Peter, Sanghvi, & Narendran, 2020).

Further into the bargain is the pronounced shortage of skilled as well as unskilled workers in the Kerala labour market, precipitated by a combination of factors comprising the rapidly ageing native population, expanding higher educational attainment and large-scale emigration of Keralites to foreign countries in search of better educational and employment opportunities, as discussed in the previous sections. As per estimates of the Kerala Planning Board (Kerala Planning Board, 2021a), by 2051, one-third of Kerala's population would be over the age of 60 years. Also, the significant growth clocked in the construction sector coupled with the absence of natives in the traditional sector workforce as well as their turning down of jobs of unskilled nature owing to enhanced aspirations, testifies the proposition that the future of Kerala belongs to migrant workers.

Hence it does not come off as a surprise that as of 2022, the two longest migration corridors in India originates from the Kottayam and Kollam districts in Kerala and ends at the Dibrugarh and Nagaon districts in Assam respectively, covering a distance of approximately 3500 kilometres (Asianet News, 2022).

What Sets the Kerala Model Apart?

On the part of the state, Kerala has rolled out a host of social welfare schemes for its "guest workers", (as migrant workers are officially recognized by the state) including the drawing up of the widely acclaimed Migrant Welfare Policy of 2010,

the Awas Insurance Policy (2017), Apna Ghar Residential Scheme (2019) as well as fourteen literacy and educational schemes, comprising the flagship “Hamara Malayalam” programme. At this juncture, due acknowledgement needs to be given to some of the notable schemes implemented by other states as well. For instance, Jharkhand has launched the *Shramdhan* portal, which is essentially a ‘Comprehensive Labour Management System’ aimed at inter-linking the industries and labour, besides ensuring financial inclusion and labour registration. Similarly, Odisha has launched the *Shramik Sahayath* a helpline to aid workers in distress. Another significant initiative is the *Karmasathi* scheme as envisaged by West Bengal for the resolution of problems faced by migrant workers in the course of their employment outside the state and providing various assistances, including financial compensation on account of death, accidental injury, besides other assistance to mitigate issues related to wage, abuse, trafficking or even exigencies like natural calamities and pandemic situation.

Given that, what sets the efforts of Kerala apart from the initiatives undertaken by other host states is that, while the latter try to situate their policies and programmes for inter-state migrant workers within the obligations set out by the provisions of the Inter-State Migrant Workmen Act 1979, Kerala, in contrast, has stepped out of the confines of the act to innovate schemes that go well beyond the mere concept of welfare to the holistic development of migrant workers and their families. This fact is vindicated by the *Interstate Migrant Policy Index (IMPEX)* (Aggarwal, Singh, & Singh, 2019) Report 2019 released by the NGO *India Migration Now*, in which Kerala came out to be the most migrant-friendly state, with the indicators on child rights protection, education, health and sanitation scoring high.

However, despite the commendable efforts undertaken by the state, the fundamental challenge of migrant workers being regarded as *de facto* citizens persists here as in the case of other states in India. Hence, there exists an urgent need to identify and analyse those yet-to-be-addressed challenges so as to bridge the policy gaps and thereby take the welfare measures intended for the migrant workers to the last mile.

But Challenges Still Persist

The primary challenge as identified by the ANRF project has been the elusivity of reliable statistical data to ascertain the exact population of migrant workers in the State. While studies undertaken by the Kerala Planning Board peg the count at 34 lakhs, as per official databases of the State Government, the numbers hover around a little over 5 lakhs. This gross mismatch presents an alarming situation as accurate data regarding the population of migrant workers is an essential prerequisite for developing effective policies and programmes.

Secondly, as in any other state, a sizeable fraction of migrant workers is employed in precarious occupations such as in construction sites, plywood factories, crushing units and brick kilns. Unscientific methods of production and deplorable working conditions, coupled with the apathy of employers and contractors towards complying with the necessary safety standards in these worksites, often render migrant workers vulnerable to life-threatening conditions. According to official estimates, over 150 workers have died in the course of their work in the last 7 years in the state (Kerala State Planning Board, 2023). What is worse is the predicament of those workers who are rendered maimed while on the job. Not only are they terminated from employment but also denied fair compensation, thereby infringing on their rights besides leaving them incapacitated for their lifetime. While both the above-mentioned circumstances force the families of the affected migrant workers into poverty, an even more horrifying spectacle unfolds when the former find themselves incapable of transporting the mortal remains of the deceased workers to their native places due to a lack of financial resources. A grim picture of work-related exploitation extending to denial of justice post-death is unveiled here.

Thirdly, our fieldwork revealed that exploitation by employers and contractors also takes the form of underpayment or even delayed payment of wages. This comes on top of the widely acknowledged fact that migrant labourers are paid grossly less than native workers (Khadar & Bijulal, 2023). The lack of collective bargaining power to negotiate their wages as in the case of local trade unions further aggravate their situation. Through an intersectional lens, one can view that still deplorable is the physical and mental torture faced by female migrant workers in the unorganised sector. It is estimated that more than 1000 migrant women are employed in the state across various sectors, including domestic work and construction activities. The challenges encountered by them range from finding safe accommodation to job security and even sexual abuse at the hands of their employers and contractors (Khadar & Deepak, 2023).

The above-discussed challenges directly bring us to the fourth major hurdle faced by migrant workers and their families, that of accessing legal justice. Apathy on the part of the police as well as the labour department towards the issues faced by the migrant workers, despite these being brought to the former's notice by the aggrieved parties themselves, presents a graver challenge. Often, reluctance exhibited by both departments in initiating timely action against the erring employers or contractors leaves the workers with no other option but to take legal recourse. At this point, a lack of proficiency in the native language of the state presents the first major barrier. Also, while the aggrieved workers are forced to bear the expenses for seeking legal remedy by themselves, in the case of deceased workers, their relatives are compelled to travel to the destination state in order to fight the case for granting fair compensation. Further, delays in the filing

of chargesheets by the police department and prolonged case trial periods, add to the woes of these impoverished families, pushing them to penury.

The fifth major challenge stems from the execrable living conditions of the children of migrant workers. It has been observed that parents are forced to carry their toddlers, even to hazardous worksites such as plywood companies and brick factories, owing to lack of caregivers at home or adequate daycare facilities at their worksites. Our field visit based understanding is that even older children are prevented from attending schools due to reasons ranging from inflexible working hours of parents, which hovers around 12 hours per day, to caregiving responsibilities towards their younger siblings. This scenario often compels children to stay back with their parents at the worksites, thereby robbing them off a healthy childhood as promised by Article 39 (f) of the Indian Constitution. Also, cases of accidental deaths of migrant children at work sites have been reported from across the state. Moreover, as per Government records, as many as 900 children in Ernakulam district and 500 in Idukki do not attend schools, despite the Constitution providing for the Right to Free and Compulsory Elementary Education under Article 21A (Kerala State Planning Board, 2021). While the lack of adequate commutation facilities and the burden of household chores restrain children from attending schools, non-possession of Aadhar cards, unfamiliarity with the local language that hinders smooth communication as well as the prevalent social biases against migrant children, often tagged in local parlance as “*Bhai Children*”, prevent the schools from admitting them. Apparently, a case of violation of the Right to Education (RTE) Act, 2019 (GoI 2019), which mandates proactive efforts on the part of the State to ensure free and compulsory education to all children below 14 years of age, is evident here.

Finally, the severe apathy as exhibited by labour officers in taking necessary steps to redress the grievances faced by migrant workers such as non-payment of wages as well as their lackadaisical attitude towards fulfilling official responsibilities, including the inspection of worksites, proves to be a major cause of concern. A prime reason for the above scenario, as revealed by our study, is the gross disproportion between the number of labour officers and the migrant worker population within their respective jurisdictions. For instance, the ratio may be as low as 1 officer to 10,000 workers as in the case of the Perumbavoor municipality in Ernakulam district. Despite the labour supply rising steadily over the years, the labour department is yet to undergo the much-needed reforms accordingly. Labour office circles continue to remain demarcated based on the number of shops included within its jurisdictional area as of 10 years ago. The miserable worker-to-officer ratio, thus precipitated, makes it cumbersome for the latter to attend to the complex issues faced by migrant workers on par with the existing challenges that

are being dealt with.

The Emerging Integration Crisis

A study conducted by the *Centre for Migration Policy and Inclusive Governance* (Bijulal & Khadar, 2023) at Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala, on the increasing instances of migrant workers becoming victims of intolerance, has revealed a spike in fake news and narratives against them across the state's news and social media platforms. The rise of xenophobic tendencies against migrant workers in local newspapers and social media platforms has resulted in rendering them insecure in the state. The various mob-lynching episodes, though sporadic, such as the most recent ones involving Rajesh Manji, a native of Bihar and Ashok Das who hailed from Arunachal Pradesh, allegedly for engaging in theft, stand to vindicate the pressing need for deliberations on the insecurity created by migrant workers in Kerala's public discourse centres and concrete efforts to integrate them into the society for harmonious coexistence (Bijulal & Khadar, 2024). While it is a fact that violence perpetrated by migrant workers tends to generate strong sentiments against them in Kerala's public conscience, it becomes imperative for the government to decode as to how *safe, orderly and regular migration* as envisaged in the UN Global Compact on Migration (IOM 2018) may be realized. What is perceptible is the indispensability of formulating a comprehensive immigration policy that suits the changing socio-economic scenario of the state.

Policy Suggestions

Based on extensive field studies undertaken across all 14 districts of Kerala, involving focus group discussions and in-depth interviews with members of the migrant worker communities as well as detailed discussions with policymakers, government and civil society representatives, the following policy recommendations are suggested.

Registration of interstate migrant workers as well as administration of various health and welfare services due to them continue to be centralized functions under the Kerala Labour Commissionerate. This arrangement has often precipitated the situation of the beneficiaries not being able to gain access to adequate services, as also timely information regarding their rights and entitlements. Therefore, implementing a decentralized data collection and dissemination system by roping in the robust local self-government institutions in Kerala would go a long way in bridging this crucial information and service delivery gap.

As the first step in this direction, undertaking a systematic census of the migrant population in the state at the panchayat and ward-levels as has been

directed by the state government needs to be expedited. For this purpose, panchayat and ward members may be tasked to spearhead the process in liaison with the local Kudumbashree units, whose members may carry out the population surveys in their respective localities.

Further, every panchayat and municipality should be empowered to impose a monthly working tax on interstate migrant workers within their jurisdiction, while in turn being charged with ensuring the systematic registration, accommodation, access to sanitation, health and legal services for the tax-paying migrant workers. In this way, a thematic information database with respect to the migrant community in the state would be made available to the government, beyond sheer quantitative data on their numbers, that would aid in informed and evidence-based policy making.

Thirdly, interstate agreements on data exchange may be promoted to ensure smooth migration. Besides providing for identification of migrants with criminal backgrounds in the destination states, such arrangements would also help in securing social welfare and legal aid to the workers as well as their families, both in the source as well as the destination states. To this effect, appointment of a liaison officer by the respective state of origin of the migrant workers in the host state, can serve as a vital step in bridging any information or communication gap, thereby aiding in effortless coordination between the two states for the purpose of migrant welfare.

That being said, surveys carried out by the ANRF project has revealed that three out of every ten migrant workers to Kerala aspire to settle down permanently in the state. Hence, efforts to ensure inclusion of migrant workers at the institutional level needs to be bolstered. In this direction, steps should be taken to furnish the necessary documents by the state government to those workers desirous of settling down permanently in Kerala. Domicile certificates should be issued to migrant labourers who have been residing in the state for a period of at least five years.

In order to ensure a healthy environment for the all-round development of migrant children, daycare facilities, which match the work timing of the parents, need to be provided at the worksites. Also, bridge schools should be established, so as to integrate the migrant children with the state curriculum, thereby securing their right to education. Further, access to public employment and opportunities for higher education should also be made available to the children of migrant workers. This may be realized by harnessing education subsidies and establishment of cess funds dedicated for the purpose.

Given that, systemic integration of the migrant workforce should be secured by providing them with access to all kinds of institutional benefits and processes,

including policy formulation and elections. To begin with, consultative policy-making may be actualized by setting up representative committees comprising migrant workers, members of the civil society and local self-government institutions, which may provide policy inputs based on ground reality to various expert committees constituted at the state-level for the purpose of drawing up programmes and action plans for the welfare of the migrant labour force. Such a bottom-up approach would not only ensure evidence-based policy making, but also warrant that the voices of the marginalised migrant communities are bought to the table. Moving forward, a transition towards participatory policy-making may be realised by gradually integrating domiciled migrant communities into the Gram Sabhas and Ward Sabhas, besides also providing for their representation in local area development forums.

Further, in the realm of political integration, restoration of the constitutional right to vote to the migrant population is of paramount importance. Political disenfranchisement of an already socio-economically marginalized cohort, would only serve to aggravate their alienation, question their citizenship rights and above everything devalue the economic force they constitute in forging the country's growth story. In this regard, remote voting options in both electronic and non-electronic forms need to be proactively implemented by the concerted effort of the Union and State governments. Amendment of the Representation of People Act, 1951 so as to incorporate migrant workers as a 'class of citizens' to whom postal ballot voting may be extended is the need of the hour. Also, pilot projects on the Electronically Transmitted Postal Ballot System (ETPBS), as considered by the Election Commission of India, may be undertaken and if found viable, be scaled-up, thereby realizing universal adult suffrage. In addition, facilitation of proxy voting rights as well as establishment of special polling booths in the host state may also be considered for implementation. Apart from enhancing voter turnout, the above measures have far-reaching ramifications in deepening democracy by way of transforming the hitherto marginalised migrant workforce into a significant political force, whose opinions and demands carry due weight in the political discourse of the country.

On the health front, a unique model encompassing universal coverage may be conceived and executed based on best practices drawn from existing schemes. To this extent, Primary Health Centres/Community Health Centres may conduct free medical camps on a chosen day every month, exclusively for migrant workers and their families residing in their respective localities. Voluntary services by interested private medical practitioners may also be encouraged in such camps. Besides, compulsory service of doctors in primary health centres during night hours should be ensured to suit the mostly inflexible daily working hours of migrant workers.

Further, mobile medical units that can take medical aid to the remotest areas may be deployed. A public-private partnership model may be sought to actualize the same, emulating the successful example of the CMID (Centre for Migration and Inclusive Development) health van, a joint venture implemented under the National Health Mission (NHM) and funded by the Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited's (BPCL) Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiative. Also, selected cohort of female migrant workers across every panchayat or ward may be imparted training on the models of ASHA workers (link workers) and ANMs to cater to the primary as well as emergency medical needs of the migrant community, especially women and children.

Another crucial aspect of migrant welfare that needs to be dealt with is that of ensuring access to legal aid and protection. Although the Indian Constitution under Article 14 guarantees the fundamental right to equality before law and equal protection of laws, most migrant workers are ignorant of their legal rights, besides facing difficulties in navigating the complex legal system. In addition, lack of proficiency in the native language of the destination state further aggravates their vulnerability. Establishment of legal aid clinics in areas having high concentrations of migrant workforce can be a major step forward in providing them with the necessary legal support and guidance. Also, services of Pro Bono lawyers and social workers, sharing the necessary proficiency in the native language of the migrant workers, must be made available in such clinics complying with the Directive Principle as envisaged in Article 39A. Further, every employer or contractor must be mandated through proper legislation to make provision for disseminating complete information regarding the legal rights and entitlements (in respect of both the Union and the respective State laws) of migrant workers employed by them. This may be carried out through in-person orientation at the time of hiring as well as circulating printed handouts detailing the same in the language comprehensible to the workers. Additionally, setting up of helplines and mobile legal aid units can contribute towards ensuring timely intervention during instances of exploitation or abuse. Also, a dedicated tribunal for adjudication of disputes, claims or such other matters concerning migrant workers needs to be established at the state level for expediting the process of disposing off the same in the shortest possible timeframe.

Apart from social and political inclusion, cultural integration with the host society assumes utmost significance when it comes to ensuring migrant welfare. To foster socio-cultural cohesion, the administrative machinery may partner with local NGOs and community organisations in promoting programmes aimed at building bridges between migrant workers and the native communities. Initiatives such as cultural exchange programmes and community festivals may be organised to promote mutual understanding and respect. Also, the local libraries that form

a vital aspect of the social life in Kerala, may be harnessed as a means of cultural integration by way of holding books published in the native language of the migrant workers, organising community reading sessions as well as language classes to familiarise each other with their respective cultures. An exemplary initiative in this regard is the Hindi language classes for the native people as initiated by the Chelannoor Village Panchayat in Calicut District, aimed at enabling the local population to converse easily with the migrant labour force who are increasingly replacing the natives in almost all spheres of daily life, from local grocery shops to salons and spas. The Panchayat aspires to attain total Hindi literacy by the Republic Day of 2025. By way of encouraging interaction and collaboration between the migrant populace and the native communities, these efforts promise to mitigate social tensions and thereby create a more inclusive and harmonious environment.

Besides the above, a detailed survey needs to be undertaken by the Government in conjunction with the civil society to ascertain the reasons that prevent the full-fledged integration of migrants into the Kerala society, be it cultural or psychological, and devise measures for trust-building between the communities. This initiative would help curb the growing tendency to generalise migrants as criminals, on the basis of sporadic incidents of them being charged with murder and narcotic cases, in the public discourse of Kerala.

In the sphere of food security, to address the challenges hindering the smooth implementation of the One Nation, One Ration Card scheme, a unified migrant residential ownership database needs to be created to identify the beneficiaries across the states. This database should be regularly updated and made accessible to all relevant stakeholders. Secondly, the Central Government should take steps to simplify the Aadhaar registration procedures for ration card applicants, in order to reduce instances of registration failures in the PDS system. Standardizing portable distribution systems across states would ensure consistency and interoperability, thereby facilitating seamless access to ration for migrant workers. Additionally, expanding the variety of nutritious food items in the PDS basket and ensuring their availability is crucial to meet the nutrition requirements of the beneficiaries. Finally, establishing a robust monitoring and evaluation mechanism would enable the government to track the progress in the implementation of the scheme and address any identified issues promptly. Through the above discussed measures, the government can secure equitable access to ration and promote food security for all citizens, particularly the migrants as well as other vulnerable populations.

Lastly, effective monitoring and evaluation of the policies and programmes for migrant workers is essential to ensure positive outcomes and address issues that emerge from time to time. Studies have revealed that though several schemes exist for the welfare of migrant labourers in Kerala when compared with other

states of India, their benefits are far from reaching them adequately. In this regard, establishing a dedicated body to oversee the implementation of migrant welfare schemes should be considered. To this effect, a separate department on the lines of NORKA may be established or the existing NORKA Department may be expanded to look into the administration of welfare schemes as well as grievance redressal of the migrant workers in the state. Further, transparency in the allocation and utilization of resources provided by the Central and State Governments must be ensured by subjecting the accounts of various schemes concerning migrant workers to social auditing. Also, regular impact assessments and feedback mechanisms involving migrant workers can help refine policies and ensure that they meet the needs of the intended beneficiaries.

Conclusion

Experience from around the globe suggests that migration is both a development challenge as well as a force for prosperity at the same time. Findings of the ANRF project also vindicate that Kerala is set to witness a sustained inflow of migrant labour in the next twenty years (Bijulal & Khadar, 2024), a prospect that promises a steadily increasing contribution to the state's Gross Domestic Product (GSDP), as they are projected to spend around 10,000 crore rupees per year towards necessities ranging from rent to groceries to reside in the state. Simultaneously, migration to Kerala is also transforming hundreds of villages across India by lifting them out of severe poverty and offering better living standards by way of remittances, analogous to how large-scale migration to the Gulf countries by Keralites in the 1970s transformed the state's economy. As such, evidence-based targeted policy interventions evolved through an inclusive and participatory mechanism is the need of the hour. As inter-state migrant workers continue to become the primary labour force in Kerala, the onus is ultimately on the government to craft policies to accommodate their influx and ensure their integration into the Kerala Society, thereby duly acknowledging their invaluable contribution in forging the New Kerala.

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest regarding the research, authorship, or publication

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